

Population Dynamics of Fiddler Crab Assemblage in Mangrove Ecosystem: A Modelling Approach

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Abstract

This research work focused on investigating the population dynamics of the fiddler crab in an ecosystem with effect of predation, habitat loss and availability of food resources. A predator-prey model for the population dynamics of the fiddler crab as well as the existence of food resources was developed. The population of the prey (fiddler crab) was divided into two sub-populations: male and female. The model included three set of predators (Herons, Egrets and Raccoons). We established the region where the model (16) is biologically feasible and mathematically well posed. The analytical result reveals that the coexistence equilibrium is locally asymptotically stable if the recovery potentials $R_m < 1$ and $R_f < 1$. Numerical simulations revealed that: predation rate affects the population of the prey population negatively, the population size is negatively dependent on the rate of habitat loss and the rate of food availability will determine the level of growth and maturation of the prey population.

Keywords: fiddler crabs, predation, habitat loss, reproduction rate, food resources, recovery potential.

Introduction

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Mangroves are one of the most productive ecosystems on the planet (Michaud et al., 2023), safeguarding coastlines, fostering marine life, and providing rearing habitats for many species of fish, shellfish, and wildlife (Santos et al., 2014). They support a unique ecosystem providing shelter and food for motile fauna such as prawns and crabs (Zamboni et al., 2022; Nagelkerken et al., 2008). As a coastal habitat, they account for 14% of carbon sequestration (Alongi, 2012).

Within these intricate ecosystems, the role of macrofauna, such as the mangrove crab *Uca tangeri*, remains paramount in maintaining the delicate balance and functioning of these coastal habitats (Alongi, 2008). In tropical regions, different fiddler crabs coexist on the mangrove floor (Mokthari et al., 2015), establishing dense populations in these intertidal flats. *Uca* species increase sediment drainage and soil redox potential, translocate organic matter, and increase the sediment surface area through crawling, foraging, and burrowing activities. (Penha-Lopes et al., 2009). Thus, they are essential in stimulating microbial metabolism, organic matter degradation, nutrient cycling, and flora productivity (Gribshot and Penha-Lopes). Despite the broad effects of fiddler crabs on mangrove ecosystems, few studies have focused on their population dynamics (i.e., growth, mortality, and recruitment rates) and mathematical relationship governing their abundance, distribution, and interaction, paving the way for informed decision-making in mangrove ecosystem management.

Several models have been used to describe the predator-prey relationship. The predator-prey model is a representation of the interaction between two species of animals that live in the same ecosystem whereby the quantity of each group of these species depends on the birth or death rate and the successful meetings with the individuals of the other species (Restrepo and Sánchez, 2010). Heberman, R. (2007) developed mathematical models describing the relationship between plants, animals and their environment (Ecology). His model formulation was based on the observed population data of the various species such as human population in a specific area or the population of fish and algae in a lake he also highlights that to formulate a population model effectively some factors need to be considered for instance, the population of sharks depends on some factors including the number of fish, harmful bacteria, water temperature, salinity and many more. Moreover, Lambert et al. (2010) highlighted that population modelling is an application of differential equations in studying and understanding the changes in population of species in an ecosystem. They further stated that ecological population modelling is concerned with the changes in a population as a result of interaction between the organism and the physical environment. It is

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also concerned with interaction between the organisms and individuals of either the same or different species.

Moreover, Li (2011) studied the Lotka-Volterra model with two species where he used the Matlab function to approximate numerically the solution of the Lotka-Volterra model. He also analysed the asymptotic behaviour of the solutions. On the other hand, Vaidyanathan (Vaidyanathan, S., 2010) investigated the nonlinear observer design for Lotka-Volterra models where he employed Sundarapandian's theorem (2002) to solve the problem of observer design for Lotka-Volterra model. He studied two species and three species predator-prey models to construct the nonlinear observers for these Lotka-Volterra models. Consequently, Dayar and Mikeev (2010) employed the analysis of Lotka-Volterra model where they emphasised that it is highly challenging because it shows strong fluctuation and hence becomes unstable at the end. Thus, due to this flexibility, traditional numerical techniques are not appropriate enough to solve the model. Therefore, they have suggested the adaptations and combinations of the traditional technique in order to have fast, effective, reliable and accurate results for some parameter ranges of the Lotka-Volterra model.

Chauvet et al (2002) Investigated modelling the ecosystem of the three dimensional Lotka-Volterra model with the linear three-species food chain where the prey (x) is consumed by a middle level species (y). Meanwhile, this species-y is then prey upon by a top level predator z. However, the examples of such three-species ecosystems include mouse-snake-owl.

By focusing on the interactions between species abundance, environmental parameters, and habitat characteristics, this study aims to employ a population-based modeling approach to delve into the intricate dynamics of *Uca tangeri* populations within the mangrove ecosystem. Specifically, we asked the following questions: (1) How does predation affect the population of fiddler crabs? (2) What is their relative net biomass in the mangrove ecosystem? (3) How does the growth rates of male and female differ? (4) How does habitat loss affect the population of the fiddler crabs? (5) Does food availability affect their net biomass production rates?

2 Model Formulation

in this section, we develop a mathematical model to describe the population dynamics of fiddler crab in a habitat where there is predation and habitat loss. Before the development, we make the following assumptions.

2.1 Basic Assumptions

In order to formulate an appropriate mathematical model, that captures the population dynamics of the fiddler crab, the following assumptions were made

- We assume that immature crabs (megalope) are introduced into the habitat following maturation from the zoey stage and with the available food resources to grow into juvenile and adult.
- The immature and juvenile crabs utilize all energy for growth and maturation.
- We assume that the adult fiddler crabs do not grow but invest all energy in reproduction. The male invest energy in mating while the female does the reproduction.
- Maturation rates depend on the net biomass production rate.
- The growth rate and reproduction rates of the fiddler crabs depends on food availability as well as the nature of the habitat.
- Fiddler crabs are semi-aquatic (they live both in water and on land), hence, their food resources are found both on land and water.
- The net biomass production rates of fiddler crab for juveniles and adults are assumed to equal the balance between the ingestion and maintenance rate.
- At low densities, the energy intake of juveniles and adults is insufficient to cover their maintenance requirements. Thus, adult fiddler crabs only produce biomass when their food intake is sufficient to cover their maintenance requirement.
- We assume an equal natural mortality for all males and females. An equal natural mortality is also assumed for the predator population.
- We assume two habitats (land and water) with two food sources (plant and animal food sources).

2.2 Model Description

In this section, we consider two populations; the predator and the prey population. The predator population at time t , is divided into the following groups; Heron(H), Egrets(E) and Raccoons(R). so that the total population is given by

$$N_P(t) = H(t) + E(t) + R(t) \tag{1}$$

The prey (fiddler crab) population is divided into immature male crabs (I_m), immature female crabs (I_f), juvenile male crabs (J_m), juvenile female crabs (J_f), adult male crabs (A_m) and adult female crabs (A_f). Thus, for the prey population, we have

$$N_r(t) = I_m(t) + I_f(t) + J_m(t) + J_f(t) + A_m(t) + A_f(t) \tag{2}$$

Two food sources are used to capture the semi-aquatic nature of fiddler crabs; food sources from plant and animals (F_A and F_P respectively)

2.2.1 Equations Governing Food Sources

For the equations governing the food sources, we use the equations given by De Roos et. al. (2008) to develop the growth rates of the food sources F_A and F_P . the food source (animal based), F_A follows the logistic growth rate given by

$$G_A = r_A F_A \left(1 - \frac{F_A}{k(1-c)}\right) \tag{3}$$

Where r_A is the intrinsic growth rate, k is the carrying capacity of food resources and c measures the rate of habitat loss. Due to external influx and spatial conditions such as coverage, not all food resources are available to the fiddler crab population. The crabs cannot reach all animal food resources, F_A on land and in water. Thus, we introduce a threshold constant Λ_a . so that the available animal food resources is defined by

$$\widehat{F}_A = F_A - \Lambda_a \cong \max(0, F_A - \Lambda_a) \tag{4}$$

In the same vein, the food resources (plant based), F_P follows a semi-chemostat growth rate G_P given by

$$G_P = r_P(k(1-c) - F_P) \tag{5}$$

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Where r_p is the intrinsic growth rate, k is the carrying capacity of the ecosystem as mentioned earlier and c measures the rate of habitat loss.

2.2.2 Equations for Vital Rates

We also adopt De Roos et al. (2008) derivation of net biomass production rates of the population of the fiddler crabs at different stages. The net biomass production rates of immature crabs, juvenile crabs and adult fiddker crabs are given by

$$\lambda_{mi} = \sigma_{mi}I_{mi}(Q + (1-Q)P) - T$$

$$\lambda_{fi} = \sigma_{fi}I_{fi}(Q + (1-Q)P) - T$$

$$\lambda_{mj} = \sigma_{mj}I_{mj}(Q + (1-Q)P) - T$$

$$\lambda_{fj} = \sigma_{fj}I_{fj}(Q + (1-Q)P) - T \tag{6}$$

$$\lambda_{ma} = \sigma_{ma}I_{ma}(Q + (1-Q)P) - T$$

$$\lambda_{fa} = \sigma_{fa}I_{fa}(Q + (1-Q)P) - T$$

And

$$Q = \frac{\widehat{F}_A}{H_c + \widehat{F}_A} + \frac{\widehat{F}_A}{L + \widehat{F}_A} \tag{7}$$

$$P = \frac{\widehat{F}_p}{H_c + \widehat{F}_p} + \frac{\widehat{F}_p}{L + \widehat{F}_p}$$

Where σ_{mi} , σ_{mj} , σ_{ma} (σ_{fi} , σ_{fj} , σ_{fa}) are the conversion efficiency of food injected by the male immature crabs, juvenile and adult crabs (female immature, juvenile and adult female crabs) respectively. The parameters I_{mi} , I_{mj} , I_{ma} (I_{fi} , I_{fj} , I_{fa}) are the maximum ingestion rates per unit biomass of male immature, juvenile and adult (female immature, juvenile and adult) crabs respectively. The parameter H_c measures the half saturation food level of fiddler crabs in water and L measures the level of spread of food resources on land.

2.2.3 Equations for Maturation

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For the maturation of the fiddler crab population, we use the function

$$\mathbf{m}(\sigma, \mu, z) = \frac{\sigma - \mu}{1 - z^{1 - \frac{\mu}{\sigma}}} \quad (9)$$

$$\mathbf{f}(\sigma, \mu, z) = \frac{\sigma - \mu}{1 - z^{1 - \frac{\mu}{\sigma}}}$$

we now define the following maturational rates for the fiddler crab population

Zoey male crab → Immature male crab

$$M_z = m(\mu_m, \sigma_{mz}, \frac{p_z}{p_i}) \quad (10)$$

Immature male crab → Juvenile male crab

$$M_i = m(\mu_m, \sigma_{mi}, \frac{p_i}{p_j}) \quad (11)$$

Juvenile male crab → Adult male crab

$$M_j = m(\mu_m, \sigma_{mj}, \frac{p_j}{p_a}) \quad (12)$$

Similarly, the maturation function for the female fiddler crab population is given thus;

Zoey female crab → Immature female crab

$$F_z = f(\mu_f, \sigma_{fz}, \frac{q_z}{q_i}) \quad (13)$$

Immature female crab → Juvenile female crab

$$F_i = f(\mu_f, \sigma_{fi}, \frac{q_i}{q_j}) \quad (14)$$

Juvenile female crab → Adult female crab

$$F_j = f(\mu_f, \sigma_{fj}, \frac{q_j}{q_a}) \quad (15)$$

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2.2.4 Derivation of Model Equations

On the basis of our assumptions, the fiddler crab model with maturation, predators and two food sources is given by the following system of non-linear ordinary differential equations

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{dI_m}{dt} &= \Lambda_m + \lambda_{mi}A_m - (p_1H + p_2E + p_3R + m_i + \mu_m)I_m \\ \frac{dJ_m}{dt} &= m_iI_m + \lambda_{mj}A_m - (a_1H + a_2E + a_3R + m_j + \mu_m)J_m \\ \frac{dA_m}{dt} &= m_jJ_m - (b_1H + b_2E + b_3R + \mu_m)A_m \\ \frac{dI_f}{dt} &= \Lambda_f + \lambda_{fi}A_f - (p_1H + p_2E + p_3R + f_i + \mu_f)I_f \\ \frac{dJ_f}{dt} &= f_jI_f + \lambda_{fj}A_f - (a_1H + a_2E + a_3R + f_j + \mu_m)J_f \\ \frac{dA_f}{dt} &= f_jJ_f - (b_1H + b_2E + b_3R + \mu_f)A_f \\ \frac{dH}{dt} &= \Lambda_h + p_1I_m + a_1J_m + b_1A_m + p_1I_f + a_1J_f + b_1A_f - \mu \\ \frac{dE}{dt} &= \Lambda_e + p_2I_m + a_2J_m + b_2A_m + p_2I_f + a_2J_f + b_2A_f - \mu \\ \frac{dR}{dt} &= \Lambda_r + p_3I_m + a_3J_m + b_3A_m + p_3I_f + a_3J_f + b_3A_f - \mu \\ \frac{dF_A}{dt} &= r_A F_A \left(1 - \frac{F_A}{k(1-c)}\right) - R_A \widehat{F}_A \\ \frac{dF_P}{dt} &= r_P (k(1-c) - f_p) - R_P F_P \end{aligned} \tag{16}$$

The flow diagram for model (16) is shown in figure 1. The associated variables and parameters together with their baseline values are given in table 1 and 2 respectively.

Table 1: Variables used in model (16)

Variables	Description
$I_m(I_f)$	Biomass of immature male (female) fiddler crabs
$J_m(J_f)$	Biomass of juvenile male (female) fiddler crabs
$A_m(A_f)$	Biomass of adult male (female) fiddler crabs
H	Population of Herons
E	Population of egrets
R	Population of Raccoons
F_A	Animal food source
F_P	Plant food source

Table 2: Parameter baseline values

Parameter	Description	Baseline values	Source
$\sigma_{mi}(\sigma_{fi})$	Conversion efficiency rate for male (female) immature crabs	0.5	Yodzis and innes (1992)
$\sigma_{mj}(\sigma_{fj})$	Conversion efficiency rate for male (female) juvenile crabs	0.5	Yodzis and innes (1992)
$\sigma_{ma}(\sigma_{fa})$	Conversion efficiency rate for male (female) adult crabs	0.5	Yodzis and innes (1992)
$I_{mi}(I_{fi})$	Maximum ingestion rate for immature male (female) crabs	2.93×10^{-2}	Estimated
$I_{mj}(I_{fj})$	Maximum ingestion rate for juvenile male (female) crabs	2.93×10^{-2}	Estimated
$I_{ma}(I_{fa})$	Maximum ingestion rate for adult male (female) crabs	2.93×10^{-2}	Estimated

$\Lambda_m(\Lambda_f)$	Recruitment rate of males (females)	10day ⁻¹	Assumed
$\Lambda_h, \Lambda_e, \Lambda_r$	Recruitment rate of Herons, Egrets and Raccoons	1 day ⁻¹	Assumed
Λ_a	Food threshold constant	$0.01 \times \widehat{F}_A$	Assumed
$\mu_m(\mu_f)\mu$	Natural mortality rates for male (female) and the predator population	2.65×10^{-4}	Gillooly et al. (2001)
$P_i(q_i)$	Maturation size for immature male (female) crabs	10g	Estimated
$p_j(q_j)$	Maturation size for juvenile male (female) crabs	12g	Estimated
$P_a(q_a)$	Maturation size for adult male (female) crabs	20g	Estimated
H_c	Half saturation constant	1.38×10^{-2}	Estimated
$\lambda_{mi}(\lambda_{fi})$	Biomass production rate for immature male (female) crabs	2.35×10^{-3}	Assumed
$\lambda_{ma}(\lambda_{fa})$	Biomass production rate for juvenile male (female) crabs	2.44×10^{-3}	Assumed
$P_{i(i=1,2,3)}$	Predation rates on immature male and female crabs	$0-6 \times 10^{-3}$	Assumed
$a_{i(i=1,2,3)}$	Predation rates on juvenile male and female crabs	$0-6 \times 10^{-3}$	Assumed
$b_{i(i=1,2,3)}$	Predation rates on adult male and female crabs	$0-6 \times 10^{-3}$	Assumed
$m_i(f_i)$	Maturation rates from male (female) immature crabs to juvenile crabs	-	Assumed
$m_j(f_j)$	Maturation rates from male (female) juvenile crabs to adult crabs	-	Assumed
R_a	Intrinsic growth rate of animal food source	0.15	Assumed

R_p	Intrinsic growth rate of plant food source	0.5	Assumed
K	Carrying capacity of the environment	4×10^{-3}	Assumed
C	Rate of habitat loss	2.34×10^{-6}	Assumed
L	Rate of food spread on land	$1:38 \times 10^{-2}$	Assumed
T	Maintenance rate	$2:75 \times 10^{-6}$	Assumed

2.3 Basic Properties of the Model

For model (16) to be meaningful, we show that the model is well-posed in a biologically feasible domain. The variables $I_m, I_f, J_m, J_f, A_m, A_f, H, E, R, F_A, F_P$ are living species, non-negativity ensures that they never become negative.

Boundedness

Theorem 2.1: the feasible region

$$D = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} (I_m, J_m, A_m) \in \mathfrak{R}_+^3: N_m \leq \frac{\wedge m}{\mu_m} \\ (I_f, J_f, A_f) \in \mathfrak{R}_+^3: N_f \leq \frac{\wedge f}{\mu_f} \\ H \in \mathfrak{R}_+: N_h \leq \frac{\wedge h}{\mu} \\ E \in \mathfrak{R}_+: N_e \leq \frac{\wedge e}{\mu} \\ R \in \mathfrak{R}_+: N_r \leq \frac{\wedge r}{\mu} \end{array} \right. \quad (17)$$

is positively invariant and attracts all positive solutions of model (16).

Proof

$$N(t) = I_m(t) + I_f(t) + J_m(t) + J_f(t) + A_m(t) + A_f(t) + H(t) + E(t) + R(t) + F_A + F_P \quad (18)$$

So that

$$\frac{dN}{dt} = r_A F_A \left(1 - \frac{F_A}{k(1-c)} \right) - R_A F_A + r_p (k(1-c) - F_P) - R_p F_P + \lambda_{mi} A_m + \lambda_{mj} A_m + \lambda_{fi} A_f + \lambda_{fj} A_f$$

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For any $\omega > 0$, we add $\omega N(t)$ to both sides of the above equation, which gives

$$\frac{dN}{dt} + \omega N(t) = F_A \left(r_A \left(1 - \frac{F_A}{k(1-c)} \right) + \omega \right) + R_p F_p - (R_p - \omega) F_p + (\lambda_{mi} A_m + \lambda_{mj} A_m + \lambda_{fi} A_f + \lambda_{fj} A_f + \omega)$$

$$\frac{dN}{dt} + \omega N(t) \leq R_p F_p + F_A \left(r_A \left(1 - \frac{F_A}{k(1-c)} \right) + \omega \right) \quad (19)$$

Considering the right hand side, we have

$$f(F_A) = R_p F_p + F_A \left(r_A \left(1 - \frac{F_A}{k(1-c)} \right) + \omega \right) \quad (20)$$

This is a second degree polynomial in F_A which attains its maximum value at

$$F_A = \frac{F_{Amax}(R_A + \omega)}{2R_A} \quad (21)$$

Substituting (21) into (20) gives

$$\frac{dN}{dt} + \omega N(t) \leq R_p F_p + \frac{F_{Amax}(R_A + \omega)^2}{4R_A}$$

Using product rule of differentiation on the right hand side and integrating from 0 to t on both sides, we have

$$N(t) \leq \frac{\theta}{\omega} (1 - e^{-\omega t}) + N(0) e^{-\omega t}$$

Where $N(0)$ is the total biomass at $t = 0$ and

$$\theta = R_p F_p + \frac{F_{Amax}(R_A + \omega)^2}{4R_A}$$

thus we have the bound

$$0 \leq N(t) \leq \max \left\langle N(0), \frac{\theta}{\omega} \right\rangle$$

For all $t > 0$.

Hence, the solutions of model (16) in D are confined in the region D. thus, we conclude that the model is biologically and mathematically well posed in the region D.

Theorem 2.2: the model (16) preserves positivity of solutions. This implies that the solution with positive initial conditions will remain positive for all time $t > 0$.

The ecological interpretation of this theorem is that on the one hand, if a male and a female fiddler crab is present at the beginning of simulation, then it's biomass is always positive. On the other hand, if we have high predation and mortality, the biomass might decline exponentially even towards extinction.

3. Analysis of the model

3.1 Equilibrium points

The points where the equations of model (16) equals zero are called the equilibrium points or the steady state solutions. The system has the following equilibrium points.

- *The male only fiddler crab equilibrium point: $\varepsilon_1 = (I_m, J_m, A_m, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0)$*
- *The female only fiddler crab equilibrium point: $\varepsilon_2 = (0, 0, 0, I_f, J_f, A_f, 0, 0, 0, 0)$*
- *The predator only equilibrium point: $\varepsilon_3 = (0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, H, E, R, 0, 0)$*
- *The prey only equilibrium point: $\varepsilon_4 = (I_m, J_m, A_m, I_f, J_f, A_f, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0)$*
- *The food sources only equilibrium point: $\varepsilon_5 = (0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, 0, F_A, F_p)$*
- *The coexistence equilibrium point: $\varepsilon_6 = (I_m, J_m, A_m, I_f, J_f, A_f, H, E, R, F_A, F_p)$*

3.2 Local Stability Analysis

In this section, we investigate the local stability of the equilibrium points of model (16) obtained by finding the Jacobian corresponding to the equilibrium points.

Theorem 3.1: *the equilibrium points ε_1 and ε_2 are locally asymptotically stable if $R_m < 1$, $R_f < 1$ and unstable otherwise.*

Proof

We obtain the Jacobian matrix evaluated at the equilibrium points

$$J(\varepsilon_6) = \begin{vmatrix} a_{11} & 0 & \lambda_{mi} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ m_i & a_{22} & \lambda_{mj} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & m_j & \mu_m & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & a_{44} & 0 & \lambda_{fi} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & f_i & a_{55} & \lambda_{fj} & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & f_j & \mu_f & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ p_1 & a_1 & b_1 & p_1 & a_1 & b_1 & -\mu & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ p_1 & a_1 & b_1 & p_1 & a_1 & b_1 & 0 & -\mu & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ p_1 & a_1 & b_1 & p_1 & a_1 & b_1 & 0 & 0 & -\mu & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -R_A & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & -R_P \end{vmatrix}$$

Where

$$a_{11} = m_i + \mu_m, a_{22} = m_j + \mu_m, a_{44} = f_i + \mu_f, a_{55} = f_j + \mu_f$$

The local stability of the ε_6 is investigated using the eigenvalues criteria of the Jacobian matrix. An equilibrium point is locally asymptotically stable if the Jacobian matrix evaluated at the point has negative eigenvalues and a positive determinant.

Now considering the points ε_1 and ε_2 , we have that

$$/A/ = \begin{vmatrix} -a_{11} & 0 & \lambda_{mi} \\ m_i & -a_{22} & \lambda_{mj} \\ 0 & m_j & -\mu_m \end{vmatrix} \text{ and } /B/ = \begin{vmatrix} -a_{44} & 0 & \lambda_{fi} \\ f_i & -a_{55} & \lambda_{fj} \\ 0 & f_j & -\mu_f \end{vmatrix}$$

We find /A/, which gives

$$\lambda^3 + (a_{11} + a_{22} + \mu_m)\lambda^2 + (a_{11}a_{22} + a_{11}\mu_m + a_{22}\mu_m - m_i\lambda_{mj})\lambda + a_{11}(a_{22}\mu_m - m_j\lambda_{mj}) - \lambda_{mi}m_im_j > 0$$

Now,

$$a_{11}a_{22} + a_{11}\mu_m + a_{22}\mu_m - m_i\lambda_{mj} > 0$$

$$a_{11}a_{22} + a_{11}\mu_m + a_{22}\mu_m > m_i\lambda_{mj}$$

And

$$a_{11}(a_{22}\mu_m - m_j\lambda_{mj}) - \lambda_{mi}m_im_j > 0$$

$$a_{11}a_{22}\mu_m > a_{11}m_j\lambda_{mj} + \lambda_{mi}m_im_j$$

Thus, we get

$$\left(1 - \frac{m_i\lambda_{mj}(a_{11}m_j\lambda_{mj} + \lambda_{mi}m_im_j)}{a_{11}a_{22}\mu_m(a_{11}a_{22} + a_{11}\mu_m + a_{22}\mu_m)}\right) > 0$$

The above inequality is satisfied if and only if

$$R_m = \frac{m_i\lambda_{mj}(a_{11}m_j\lambda_{mj} + \lambda_{mi}m_im_j)}{a_{11}a_{22}\mu_m(a_{11}a_{22} + a_{11}\mu_m + a_{22}\mu_m)} < 0$$

We say that R_m is the recovery potential of the male fiddler crab based on the maturation in biomass.

We now consider

$$/B/ = \begin{vmatrix} -a_{44}-\lambda & 0 & \lambda_{fi} \\ f_i & -a_{55}-\lambda & \lambda_{fj} \\ 0 & f_j & -\mu_f - \lambda \end{vmatrix}$$

Which gives the characteristic polynomial

$$\lambda^3 + (a_{55} + a_{44} + \mu_f)\lambda^2 + (a_{44}a_{55} + a_{44}\mu_f + a_{55}\mu_f - f_i\lambda_{fj})\lambda + a_{44}(a_{55}\mu_f - f_j\lambda_{fj}) - \lambda_{fi}f_if_j > 0$$

Now,

$$a_{55} + a_{44} + \mu_f > 0$$

$$a_{44}a_{55} + a_{44}\mu_f + a_{55}\mu_f - f_i\lambda_{fj} > 0$$

$$a_{44}a_{55} + a_{44}\mu_f + a_{55}\mu_f > f_i\lambda_{fj}$$

And

$$a_{44}(a_{55}\mu_f - f_j\lambda_{fj}) - \lambda_{fi}f_if_j > 0$$

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That is if $f_j > a_{44}a_{55} + a_{44}\mu_f + a_{55}\mu_f$

Thus, we get

$$\left(1 - \frac{f_i \lambda_{fj} (a_{44} f_j \lambda_{fj} + \lambda_{fi} f_i f_j)}{a_{44} a_{55} \mu_f (a_{44} a_{55} + a_{44} \mu_f + a_{55} \mu_f)}\right) > 0$$

The above inequality is satisfied if and only if

$$R_f = \frac{f_i \lambda_{fj} (a_{44} f_j \lambda_{fj} + \lambda_{fi} f_i f_j)}{a_{44} a_{55} \mu_f (a_{44} a_{55} + a_{44} \mu_f + a_{55} \mu_f)} < 0$$

Thus, R_f is the recovery potential of the female fiddler crab based on the maturation in biomass. So that we can have

$$R_{mf} = R_m \cdot R_f$$

R_{mf} is the recovery potential of the fiddler crab with growth on biomass. R_{mf} the net generational biomass production in a virgin environment (Meng et al., 2003).

4. Numerical Simulation

In this section, we simulate our system using MATLAB to investigate coexistence and stability of the fiddler crab together with the effect of maturation, predation and habitat loss. The parameters used are obtained from literature and others estimated. These values are seen in table 1 and 2.

The simulations are stable in that when positive initial values are used, the solutions approach the positive steady state which in turn shows the dynamics of the solutions to model (16).

4.1 Effect of Predation

Figure 1 shows the effect of predation on the male and female population. It shows that the population size structure may have a negative dependence on the predation rate. This negative impact occurs because of the numbers of predators in the environment. Predation majorly occurs on immature and juvenile fiddler crabs and this reduces the fraction of immature and juvenile fiddler crabs. Predation reduces if the population of the fiddler crabs

are solely aquatic. But it is pertinent to note that fiddler crabs are semi-aquatic and most times are found on land and this gives room for increased predation.

Figure 1: plot of the effect of predation on the male and female population

4.2 Effect of Food Resources on the Net Biomass of Fiddler crabs

Figure 2 shows the effect of the available of food resources (both plant and animal) on the net biomass of the fiddler crabs. The figure shows that the rate of food availability will determine their level of growth and maturation. The more available the food resources are the better their size structure, net biomass and population increase as it will better equip the female for full reproduction. From the graph, we see the size structure (red curve), the net biomass (blur curve), the total biomass (green curve) and the population size (black curve).

Figure 2: Effect of food resources on the vital rates of the fiddler crab.

4.3 Effect of Habitat Loss

Figure 3 reveals the rate at which habitat loss (c) affects the population of the fiddler crab. As human encroachment continues to occur as well as deforestation, it will reduce the population of the fiddler crab. Figure 4 actually shows the effect of loss of habitat on the female population. As the population diminishes, reproduction also reduces. This implies that the population size is negatively dependent on the rate of habitat loss. Increasing this rate will mean reducing the population size as well as the reproduction rate.

Figure 3: effect of the rate of loss of habitat on the population size. It shows the dependence of impact of habitat loss on immature crabs (black curve), juvenile crabs (yellow curve) and the adult population (blue curve).

Figure 4: The effect of loss of habitat on the female population.

5. Discussion of Result

The major aim of this work was to investigate the population dynamics of the fiddler crab in an ecosystem with effect of predation, habitat loss and availability of food resources. To

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investigate this, a predator-prey model for the population dynamics of the fiddler crab as well as the existence of food resources was developed. The population of the prey (fiddler crab) was divided into two sub-populations: male and female. The model included three set of predators (Hérons, Egrets and Raccoons). We established the region where the model (16) is biologically feasible and mathematically well posed. The analytical result reveals that the coexistence equilibrium is locally asymptotically stable if the recovery potentials $R_m < 1$ and $R_f < 1$.

Numerical simulations revealed that predation rate affects the population of the prey population negatively. Predation reduces if the population of the fiddler crabs are solely aquatic. But it is pertinent to note that fiddler crabs are semi-aquatic and most times are found on land and this gives room for increased predation. In the same vein, the population size is negatively dependent on the rate of habitat loss. Increasing this rate will mean reducing the population size as well as the reproduction rate. The rate of food availability will determine the level of growth and maturation of the prey population

We emphasize that the results of this work is based on the formulated model (16) this study can be extended to finding out the effect of climate change, sewage and waste disposal into water bodies or even the effect of temperature or seasonality on the population dynamics of the fiddler crab. Another direction for future research would be to investigate under what condition would the population of the fiddler crab go into extinction.

Conflict of Interests

The authors declare that there is no conflict of interest.

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